

THE SOCIAL LIFE OF LANGUAGE: CULTURAL MEANINGS AND SOCIAL STRUCTURES

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Abstract: *Language, our primary tool of thought and perception, is at the heart of who we are as individuals. Languages are constantly changing, sometimes into entirely new varieties of speech, leading to subtle differences in how we present ourselves to others. This revealing account brings together twelve leading specialists from the fields of linguistics, anthropology, philosophy, and psychology, to explore the fascinating relationship between language, culture, and social interaction. A range of major questions are discussed: How does language influence our perception of the world? How do new languages emerge? How do children learn to use language appropriately? What factors determine language choice in bi- and multilingual communities? How far does language contribute to the formation of our personalities? And finally, in what ways does language make us human? Language, Culture, and Society will be essential reading for all those interested in language and its crucial role in our social lives.*

Keywords: language acquisition, Multilingualism, Cultural communication.

Introduction

Professor of Anthropology in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology at Concordia University in Montreal. Trained in linguistics and anthropology, her work focuses on theories of culture and social change, on pidgins and creoles.

Studies in the social and cultural foundations of language

The aim of this series is to develop theoretical perspectives on the essential social and cultural character of language by methodological and empirical emphasis on the occurrence of language in its communicative and interactional settings, on the sociocultural grounded “meanings” and “functions” of linguistic forms, and on the social scientific study of language use across cultures. It will thus explicate the essentially ethnographic nature of linguistic data, whether

spontaneously occurring or experimentally induced, whether normative or variation, whether synchronic or diachronic. Works appearing in the series will make substantive and theoretical contributions to the debate over the sociocultural-function and structural-formal nature of language, and will represent the concerns of scholars in the sociology and anthropology of language, anthropological linguistics, sociolinguistics, and sociocultural informed psycholinguistics.

Expertise:

- Linguistic anthropology
- Pidgins and creoles (especially Solomon Islands Pijin)
- Cultural knowledge representation
- Urbanization and socio-cultural change in the Pacific

Reference

charles taylor, Department of Philosophy, McGill University john leavitt, Department of Anthropology, Université de Montréal al regna darnell, Department of Anthropology, University of Western-Ontario

Penelope brown, Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics, Netherlands

paul kay, Department of Linguistics, University of California, Berkeley

monica heller, CREFO, OISE, Université de Toronto elinor ochs, Department of Applied Linguistics, University of California, Los Angeles

bambi schieffelin, Department of Anthropology, New York University elizabeth povinelli, Department of Anthropology and the Institute for Research on Women and Gender, Columbia University paul friedrich, Committee on Social Thought, University of Chicago